

Expressive Language Challenges of DLD: What Approach Shows the Most Promise?

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Abstract

Developmental Language Disorder (DLD) is defined as a persistent neurodevelopmental condition that challenges individuals' abilities to understand and express language. Although DLD does possess distinct neurological activation patterns, it cannot solely be attributed to neurological conditions (e.g., epilepsy, cerebral palsy), neurosensory hearing impairment, any form of brain injury/lesion or environmental deprivation. Children with DLD often experience deficits in both expressive and receptive language domains. DLD has pervasive implications across the lifespan and early intervention is key to changing a trajectory of lower quality of life. This analytical review compares 20 studies to consider the most promising interventions for children with DLD to improve expressive language. The results varied greatly, even amongst same-categories of Visual Supports, Narrative Interventions, Peer-Mediated, Linguistic – Specific Interventions and a combination of these approaches. Questions of bias impacted reliability and required caution for outcome results. Multi-modality or a combination of approach did not lead to the greatest success. Larger studies did not show the effect sizes of smaller studies. This points to a need of further research in design, longitudinal studies exploring the training of practitioners applying the interventions. Consistently explicit teaching and rehearsal was essential for larger effect size. Children with DLD did not benefit from implicit teaching or mere secondary exposure to concepts weak in their profiles.

Keywords: Developmental Language Delay; DLD; Children; expressive language; intervention; narrative intervention; linguistic-specific intervention; explicit teaching; oral language; language development.

1. Introduction

Developmental Language Disorder (DLD) is defined as a persistent neurodevelopmental condition that challenges individuals' abilities to understand and express language (Bishop et al., 2017; Jensen De López et al., 2022; McGregor, 2020). Although DLD does possess distinct neurological activation patterns, it cannot solely be attributed to neurological conditions (e.g., epilepsy, cerebral palsy), neurosensory hearing impairment, any form of brain injury/lesion or environmental deprivation (Bishop et al., 2017; Broc et al., 2021; Pauls & Archibald, 2021). Children with DLD often experience deficits in both expressive and receptive language domains. Being understood by others, strengthens social and emotional wellbeing (Blaskova, 2021; Salmenlinna & Laasko, 2020). When a child struggles to speak in coherent and nuanced ways, they struggle to build relationships, problem solve and make academic gains (Cullen et al. 2024). DLD can impact many aspects of a child's life.

The rate of the prevalence of DLD is highly debated. On the low end, McGregor (2020) approximates 7.58% of American children have DLD. Carson and colleagues (2022) cited that upwards to 20% of children

are impacted by DLD. Whereas Donolato and co-authors (2023) suggest that up to 31% of individuals with expressive language delays have unknown origins. Such realities increase the risks for reading disabilities, spelling challenges (Broc, et al., 2021; McGregor, 2020) and Mathematical struggles (Moll, 2022). DLD impacts vocabulary development, sentence structure, overall language comprehension, syntax and pragmatics. As children age, demands for deeper understanding through expression, is essential for building learning skills and maintaining friendships. With weaknesses in academics and social contexts, children with DLD are more apt to develop depression (Conti-Ramsden & Botting, 2008), to be sexually assaulted (Brownlie et al., 2007) and experience lower qualities of living based upon poorer employment opportunities (Law et al., 2009).

Despite the prevalence of DLD, it is much less known and researched than less common conditions such as ASD, Cerebral Palsy (CP), Dyslexia, epilepsy (Leonard, 2014; McGregor, 2020; Norbury et al., 2016). Limited research leaves children with DLD, their parents, educators and therapists less prepared to provide the necessary supports that will help child with DLD flourish (Gladysby et al., 2022; Sadler, 2006).

There is a growing interest in the multidimensional nature of DLD because of its cognitive and linguistic attributes (Simkin & Conti-Ramsden, 2017). As we invest in learning more, we consider the interplay of genetic predispositions, neural correlates, and environments to develop interventions with efficacy and promise. These interventions must demonstrate scalability, significant effect sizes, and the potential to positively alter the developmental trajectories of children with DLD (Ebbels et al. 2019).

1.1. Early identification

Research consistently shows that timely identification of DLD leads to earlier interventions. Earlier interventions take advantage of the rapid brain development and language acquisition that occurs before the age of seven. By five years old, children that have struggled with expressive language are at-risk of falling further behind without precise evidence-based therapies. Despite missing notable language developmental milestones before reaching school, children with DLD often go undetected prior to age five (Bishop et al., 2017; Bruinsma et al., 2023). Upon entering school, Speech and Language Pathologists (SLPs) often refrain from diagnostic labels with parents and caregivers (Ash et al., 2020), furthering a gap in services and interventions during the critical window of language development (Hendrick et al., 2019). Studies indicate that untreated DLD significantly increases risks for reading disabilities, spelling challenges (Broc et al., 2021; McGregor, 2020) and Mathematical struggles (Moll, 2022). According to two studies, having DLD increased the probability of having all three concerns up to twelve times (McGregor, 2020; Moll, 2022). Additionally, Zhang and Tomblin (2000) noted that language problems, not speech problems, were strong predictors of reading comprehension and social challenges across various contexts.

Building on the challenges surrounding the early identification of children with Developmental Language Disorders (DLD), classroom teachers, that play a critical role in detection and intervention, are ill-prepared to identify spoken language problems (Gladysby, et al., 2022). While recent strides have been made for educators to recognise specific reading difficulties, teachers are less clear about the diagnostic markers for DLD. Without early identification, the necessary intervention and support required to mitigate DLD's necessitates prolonged, frequent, and intensive interventions. Failure to implement timely interventions, Tomblin and colleagues (2008) found a strong correlation of DLD (then called Language Impairment) with behavioural disorders. These behaviour disorders further lost academic opportunity. However, emerging research, exemplified by McGregor et al. (2021), underscores the transformative impact of early and comprehensive interventions in altering the developmental trajectory of children with DLD. Early identification and proactive support can provide a pivotal trajectory shift for a child grappling with DLD.

1.2. *The Mechanics of Language*

Early in development, young children learn to distinguish sound and attach meaning to those sounds. The left hemisphere of the brain actively starts understanding and creates communicational responses. By four years old, children are piecing together complex language structures. These structures unlock communication and allow children to get more of their needs met more rapidly. This in turn, prevents frustration and anxiety. Children with DLD have atypical patterns of brain connectivity. The neurocognitive or procedural deficit hypothesis suggests atypical brain lateralization of impaired neural connectivity impacting on how the language networks of the Broca's and Wernicke's areas function (Krishnan et al., 2021; McGregor et al., 2020). These activation differences can be seen on the fMRIs of those with the most severe forms of DLD (Krishnan et al., 2021). Language processing and sentence construction structures difficulties have clinicians attempting to re-wire neural pathways; thereby promoting more efficient expressive language.

There is still so much to learn about the neural and activation patterns of children with DLD. Advances are being made quickly in the convergence of neuroscience and learning. But there are never enough resources, nor time to address the underserved DLD population. As growing research amasses, a thoughtful and comprehensive review of evidence-based, impactful interventions must be analysed.

1.3. *The importance of effective treatment approaches*

Effective treatment utilization to improve expressive language skills in children with DLD cannot be understated. Ensuring that children receive appropriate and evidence-based intervention is critical to enhance communication academics and social connections (Bishop et al., 2017; Ebbels, 2019; Finestack, 2018; Forrest, et al., 2021). We know that brain plasticity is greatest when children are young. Therefore, the importance of early identification and intervention have the strongest long-term outcomes (Conti-Ramsden et al., 2018; McKean et al., 2017).

Research also supports that in language rich homes, early linguistic exposure and social interactions can act as a significant mitigation for children with DLD (Hendricks et al., 2019). During the recent pandemic, and the slow transition back to social settings, many young children's language difficulties were compounded by the reduced language production requirements of remote learning (Radville et al, 2024). McGregor and colleagues (2021) noted that the critical window for robust neuroplasticity closes quickly as children enter school-aged. Adlof and Hogan (2019) emphasized the importance of addressing both language production and comprehension. Their work showed that having these adequate foundations are necessary for future reading and writing development. We now face two years of lost interventions compounded by long waitlists delays that could have mitigated the lagging skills in expressive language for many children. Finding cost-effective, efficacious interventions for children with DLD is critical in enhancing outcomes for children with DLD.

2. Objectives of this Systematic Review

Understanding both the challenges being faced by children with DLD and the people that are trying to support them is essential (Gladsey et al., 2022; McGregor, 2020). This systemic review explores quality interventions that could be reproducible and that show promise for implementation in a wider range of settings. Using the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool, different studies are presented. Categorization of intervention methods are considered to determine if specific approaches produce higher effect sizes. Many of the studies reviewed share a focus of early intervention and are small in nature – limiting their generalisability to the broader population of individuals with DLD (Ebbels et al., 2019). Other studies explore interventions for older children. This review hopes to answer the following research questions:

1. Is there a particular form of intervention that provides the best outcomes, across studies?

2. How does report bias and selection bias impact the validity of the reported outcomes?
3. Do multi-modal approaches garner greater success?
4. What can we learn from the gaps presented by researchers for future exploration?

A systemic review of today's most current interventions offers hope for the 7-31% of children with DLD and expressive language delays (Donolato et al., 2023; McGregor, 2020). Determining where we should focus our efforts is an incredibly important task. The time is now to ensure that only the most efficacious interventions are being used, so that children with DLD can have the greatest outcomes.

3. Methodology

This review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis guidelines (Moher et al., 2015). In this review, the author focuses on Development Language Disorder (DLD), with an expressive language focus, and associated differentiating condition identified by CATALISE consortium (Bishop et al., 2017). The review focused on DLD as the presenting condition, but other conditions that were co-occurring such as ADHD or learning disorders were not considered exclusionary factors. Interventions that addressed expressive language deficits as the subset within DLD are the focus of this review. The flow chart below outlines the vast research review undertaken.

3.1. Types of studies

This review includes randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and quasi-experimental (QE) designs without randomisation. Still others were cohort analytic designs in nature but lacked control population comparisons. For those studies with control groups, Business-as-Usual (BAU) were rated as the highest quality, with cross-over waitlists (WL) as second tier, and non-controlled studies as third tier in quality. All studies included some type of effect size measure, included pre and post treatment measures and attempted to address validity and reliability testing. Studies were required to include observations from a skilled professional, and to have been focused on the outcomes of an applied intervention for expressive language. Researchers included evidence of medium to large effect sizes amongst some of their measures in order to be included in this review.

Studies included measures for oral language (expressive language) in one of the following areas: vocabulary, morpho-syntax, pragmatics, narrative or discourse. Only studies that were focused on monolingual children were considered.

3.2. Types of participants

This Analytical review focuses on children with a diagnosis of DLD or met the diagnostic criteria of DLD. For the purposes of this study, children from the ages of 3 (pre-school) to the age of 18 are included. Conditions such as Autism (ASD), Cerebral Palsy (CP), Down syndrome, Fragile X syndrome and Williams syndrome represented confounding factors, and thereby excluded. In evaluating the eligibility of a clinical study, the author examined clinical diagnosis materials included and the inclusion criteria set out by the researchers. If a child or the sample included children that were completely non-verbal, then these studies were excluded.

For larger scaled studies (across classrooms or districts of education, in particular), the study had to specifically note children with DLD. These outcome measures were disaggregated from the general population of the study. There was great variability in these disclosures, and if it was unclear, the study was excluded.

3.3. *Delivery Agents*

Due to the variability in parent/caregiver programs, and an inability to accurately account for variations in dose, frequency and implementation integrity, if these were the “therapists / delivery agents” of the intervention; these studies were excluded.

All appropriately trained professionals were included as acceptable delivery agents. They included Speech and Language Pathologists, Speech and Language Pathology Master’s students, Research Assistants with specific training related to the specific interventions, Teachers, Special Education Teachers, Specially Trained Early Education Workers and Special Education Assistants were all deemed qualified to be delivery agents of included studies. Other professionals such as communication disorder assistants or speech and language pathology assistants would have been accepted, but were not mentioned in studies reviewed.

3.4. *Settings*

This review included studies performed in clinics, private practice, university research labs and schools.

3.5. *The Timeframe Selected*

In 2017 the CATALISE consortium (Bishop et al., 2017) built consensus around a singular term to be used in describing Developmental Language Disorders. Prior to that date, there were several terms used with varying definitions, confusing the research. Therefore, in order to build consistency of language, only studies completed 2018 to present were considered.

3.6. *Risk of Bias*

All studies included were assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool and the American Academy of Neurology (AAN) Classification of evidence scheme. Each study considered selection bias, performance bias, detection bias, attrition bias and reporting bias. Study design, sample size, blinding assessment controls were considered. If the study did not include specifics related to the study’s controls for each of these areas, an unclear status was given to that criterion. This will be discussed further in the discussion section.

The author of this study is a single author and therefore poses the risk of selection bias. Using tools such as the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool is an attempt to mitigate this weakness.

3.7. *Types of Interventions*

Therapy models vary greatly for language development. Specific therapy interventions known to support children with DLD are of greater interest. For the purposes of this review, there were five types of intervention approaches considered and one type excluded. They are: Visual Supports (including augmentative and alternative communication), Narrative Interventions (including enhanced milieu teaching, conversational recasting), peer-mediated interventions, Linguistic-Specific Interventions (e.g., phonological awareness, morphological awareness training, pragmatic language interventions, development and grammar) and metacognitive strategies. Parent/Caregiver implemented language interventions were excluded. Further details about each intervention will be analysed in the discussion section.

3.8. *Intervention Models within Intervention Categories*

Improving expressive language skills in children with Developmental Language Disorder (DLD) in school and clinical settings, several evidence-based treatment approaches have been shown to be effective. The

generalization and scalability of studies have been shown to still be a challenge of the research examined within this review. Universal methods of whole-classroom based interventions are the ideal from a mobilization strategy, but the studies using this approach failed to see the outcomes they aspired for (Hutchins & Schmitt, 2023). Models of the greatest success, required direct individual interventions (Jalali-Moghadam et al., 2024) with some success found amongst same-needs paired or small group interventions (Piasta & Logan, 2023; Rinaldi et al., 2021). Narrative-Based Language Intervention (NBLI) required a great deal of modelling, recasting and repetition for spontaneous growth in length of utterances and complexities of statements (Pauls & Archibald, 2021). Integrating visuals to assist concrete learning of language interventions is an aspect that strengthens language learning for the DLD child with expressive difficulties (Ebbels et al., 2024). Peer-mediated methods of narrative practice fundamentally changes how the interventions are delivered (Goldfield, 2017) and therefore cannot be the singular approach of intervention. Pragmatic language skills training is focused on social language rules and things like turn-taking, topic maintenance and understanding social cues, can assist children not only in learning the mechanics of speaking, but provide important friendship maintenance skills (Blaskova, 2021; Conti-Ramsden et al., 2018). Phonological awareness training found in many explicit and systematic language programs within schools did show the importance of such an approach. Finally, computer-assisted language intervention is a supplemental program that can respond to the child's learning and can focus on adjusting based upon errors (Shadieff & Yang, 2020). Utilizing these approaches within the intervention categories will be examined as their impact on children with DLD and expressive language challenges.

4. Search Strategy

The search methods for the present review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines (Moher et al., 2009; see Figure 1). Eligibility criteria included:

1. The study applied an intervention plan using one or more of the following therapies: Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC), Visual Supports, Narrative Intervention, Peer-Mediated Interventions, Social Skills Training, Cognitive Communication Therapy, Phonological Awareness Training, Morphological Training, Pragmatics Intervention, Recasting, Modelling, and/or Metacognitive Strategies.
2. The study involved children or adolescents (aged 3 – 18 years) with a diagnosis of Developmental Language Disorder based on country definitions and stipulations.
3. The study applied a pre- and post-assessments, outcome measures and behavioural observations.
4. That research was published after 2017 with a cut-off date of August 2024.
5. That all research was peer reviewed and found in scholarly journals or publications.
6. Bilingual studies were excluded. As were comorbidities that would change the focus of DLD.
7. Delivery agents of parents/caregivers were excluded due to variability and confounding variables for validity and reliability testing.

First, general studies matching the criteria were reviewed. Using the words “DLD or developmental language disorder” and “intervention or therapy” and “RCT or Randomised Control Trial or Randomized Control Trial” and “expressive language”. A second search included the search parameters of “DLD or developmental language disorder” and “effect size” and “expressive language”. A third search was made for “DLD or developmental language disorder” and “systematic review or meta-analysis” and “expressive language” and “intervention”. These search parameters were used through PubMed, Cochrane, Medline, Eric, Ebscohost, ProQuest, and Google Scholar databases. Initially, 19, 935 records were resulted. Google Scholar produced the most studies. After a preliminary sorting of sources, systematic reviews were scanned for additional studies that could be added. Utilizing a snowball or network effect, additional 17 studies were added for initial review. Duplicate studies removed 4,204 articles. Using a random generator selection tool, 3,652 studies remained under consideration. Additionally, 2,135 primary reviews excluded studies based

upon titles or abstracts. Twenty-six studies were removed because the article was not peer reviewed in English or some critical data was missing or undisclosed within the publication. This left 491 studies to scrutinize for eligibility. Of those remaining, studies were eliminated for the following reasons: comorbidity with ASD, CP, epilepsy (n= 191), studies not focussing on children/teen with DLD between the ages of 3-18 years old) (n = 263), Parent/caregiver as delivery agent (n=1), Insufficient data on methodology included (n = 3) or looking at bilingual children with DLD (n=7). Studies that used parents or caregivers as the delivery agent were excluded due to the high degree of variability in implementation across training and self-reports.

Fig. 1.

PRISMA flowchart displaying the process of literature search and screening (see Moher et al., 2009). Cut-off date for publication of studies was August 2024.

4.1. Quality of Studies

4.1.1. Quality of Studies: Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool

When considering the quality of the studies under review, the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool was used. This tool assesses a study based upon its risk of bias. A low risk denotes a study that follow good methodological practices. An unclear risk of bias refers to studies that the reader cannot determine degree of risk of bias based upon information included in the publication. A high risk of bias indicates clear issues related to bias. As you can see below, there are studies included in this review that present with convenience sampling, small sample sizes and unclear or clear opportunities for biased interpretations of the data. Despite this, the author determined notable findings leading to their inclusion. Later in the discussion section, the studies will be ranked based upon the findings, highlighting some of the studies' shortcomings.

Table 1.

Cochrane Risk of Bias Analysis of included studies. Note, this tool ranks more of the studies having weaker safeguards to ensuring unbiased research and therefore valid findings.

Author and Year	Selection Bias	Performance Bias	Detection Bias	Attrition Bias	Reporting Bias	Other Bias	Overall Risk of Bias
Aguilar et al., 2018	Unclear	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low
Balthazar et al., 2020	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear
Balthazar & Scott, 2018	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low
Blaskova, 2021	High	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Unclear	High	High
Calder et al., 2020	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low
Chen et al., 2020	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	High	Unclear	High	High
Ebbels et al., 2024	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low
Eidsvag et al., 2018	Low	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear
Finestack et al., 2018	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low
Gillam et al., 2017	Unclear	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Unclear
Goldfield et al., 2022	High	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	High	High
Joffe et al., 2017	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low
Pauls & Archibald, 2021	High	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	High	High
Petersen et al., 2022	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low
Plante et al., 2019	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low
Storkel et al., 2019	Low	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear
Sutton et al., 2022	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Unclear	High	Unclear
Wada et al., 2020	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear	Low	Unclear	Unclear	Unclear
Wilcox et al., 2019	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Unclear	Low

5. Results

As different intervention methods are important for exploration, the following chart compares the intervention type, the outcome measures and the results found. The studies included share areas of question for reproducibility, expandability and replicability to broader populations. Universal tiered one design approaches do not consistently show the results that were hoped for. Individual, small sampled and uncontrolled or randomized studies show some promise, but much caution must be held based on the selective results. Green indicates studies of higher promise. Yellow indicates either lower outcomes included or areas of concern in the design of the study. The table below includes the summary of findings based upon the intervention method and results.

Across the studies included there is significant variability in design, validity/ reliability measures, outcome measures and effects. An analysis of the influence of promising studies, their replicability and long-term impact will be explored in the discussion.

5.1. Discussion

When discussing the effectiveness of the 20 studies included in this analytical review, it is important to understand some simple comparative points. The size of the study, the methods invoked, and the results are critical in determining the merit of the interventions. Simple conclusions are provided to highlight the most salient findings.

Table 2.

Summary of Studies Analysed. Green Conclusion shows most promising outcomes. Yellow denotes some promise.

Study	Objectives	Participants	Methods	Results	Conclusion
Aguilar et al. (2018)	To compare retention of target words trained with no variability vs. high variability.	N=18 (2 small groups)	Training of 20 target words with sublexical characteristics; 5 total sessions over 6 weeks. Post-treatment 3 weeks later.	High variability group demonstrated better retention, no difference during treatment phase. Significant main effect for test day, and Group \times Test Day interaction.	High variability in training enhances retention of learning.
Balthazar et al. (2020)	To compare three grammatical interventions for complex sentence intervention.	Various ages	Sentence repetition, reading aloud, identification, deconstruction, combining, generation, production, cloze production.	Significant gains in past tense use with SHAPE CODING; significant gains on CELF-4 and complex sentence probes with CSI; significant gains in relative clause production with MetaTaal.	All approaches show promise; more research needed on long-term impact, optimal dosage, and effectiveness.
Balthazar & Scott (2018)	To improve production of complex sentences through	N=30	Single-Subject Experimental Design; 1x week (40-60 min) Group 1, 2x week	Improvements in oral language and comprehension; no significant difference between 1x week and 2x	Both intervention frequencies effective; time significant in intervention outcomes.

Study	Objectives	Participants	Methods	Results	Conclusion
	explicit teaching, modeling, and imitation.		for Group 2 over 9 weeks.	9 week groups. Significant gains in adverbial and relative clauses.	
Blaskova (2021)	To analyze peer relationship impact on language production and wellbeing. All received SLP treatment.	N=14	Individual therapy in three contexts: Enhanced provision, Specialty class, Mainstream class.	No effect size reported; emphasized multimodal approach and importance of social use of language over utterance length.	Inclusive settings should consider language limitations of children with DLD. Focus on multi-modality approach without effect size. Too small to generalize.
Calder et al. (2020)	To evaluate visual supports (SHAPE CODING) using systematic cueing to teach past tense.	N=21 (TG1=11; TG2=10)	Crossover RCT design; 1x week for 10 weeks; follow-up 5 weeks post-intervention.	Significant pre-post intervention improvement for treatment group; maintained gains post-intervention. No improvement on past tense marking or 3rd person singular.	SHAPE CODING effective for teaching past tense; gains maintained post-intervention.
Chen et al. (2020)	To explore peer language effects on children with DLD or other disabilities in an inclusive classroom.	N=448	Teacher recordings on Likert Scale; whole class intervention over 1 school year.	Greater effect of peer language resources for children with disabilities; children with DLD had significantly lower scores in vocabulary, phonological memory, visuospatial memory, and sustained attention.	Peer language resources beneficial for children with disabilities; need to consider teacher/caregiver input. Significant findings but cautious interpretation needed.
Ebbels et al. (2024)	To determine efficacy threshold of individual morphosyntactic intervention using SHAPE CODING at different dosages.	N=8	Individual intervention; 30 min/week for 20 weeks. Pre/Post testing.	Post-intervention testing highly significant (Cohen d = 1.6).	Visual supports and explicit teaching effective for morphosyntax memory in DLD. Strong individual impact with sophisticated analysis.
Eidsvag et al. (2018)	To assess the impact of enhanced conversational recasting technique on	N=20 (10 individual, 10 pairs)	30 min sessions, 5 days/week for 5 weeks. Individual vs. paired learning	Significant gains in both individual (d=7.7) and group (d=5.7) therapy. No statistical difference in outcomes between individual and group	Recasting effective; paired treatment did not enhance learning of non-targeted morphemes.

Study	Objectives	Participants	Methods	Results	Conclusion
	morpheme learning.			learning. Ambient form effect size of group therapy (d=0.5).	
Finestack et al. (2018)	To compare implicit, explicit, and combination teaching methods for grammar using novel grammatical structures.	N=25	Individual treatment; 4.5 computer-based sessions over 9 days (20 min each).	Significant group differences ($p < .01$) in pattern users (PU) with highest in E-I group. Effect sizes medium to large ($\Phi_s = 0.25-0.76$).	Explicit individual instruction is more effective for Children with DLD than implicit learning. Addresses different modalities of instruction.
Gilliam et al. (2017)	To assess narrative discourse intervention program. Children retell stories. (Cards to remind to include settings, characters, actions and sequence)	N=4 Treatment 2 = BUA Individual treatment.	Phase I = 20 lessons, II = lessons until mastery, III = 12 lessons; 8 weeks; Between 10 hours, 8 mins. to 14 hours, 6 mins.	Looked at Mean Length of Utterance in Syllables (MISL) and Number of Different Words (NDW). Too small scale to generalize.	Treatment for individual was intensive and showed moderate to large improvements. Explicit teaching of components of a retell and repetition shows promise for DLD. Strong improvement metrics despite small sample.
Goldfield et al. (2022)	To assess impact of narrative intervention on productivity and complexity. To examine teacher knowledge.	N=1,362 (687 treatment; 673 control)	Whole class intervention with small group instruction. 1 school year.	Significant improvement in narrative complexity in treatment group (MISL: Tau-U = .67, $p < .01$) Nil in control. Expressive complexity: $p = .68$; effect size = 0.05.	Improved teacher knowledge did not translate to expected student growth. Larger study did not replicate smaller study (Snow et al., 2014).
Joffe et al. (2017)	To evaluate effectiveness of narrative and vocabulary interventions on storytelling and vocabulary skills.	N=358	Small Group, RCT with WL control. 18 sessions @ 45-60 mins. 3x weekly for 6 months.	Moderate improvement in storytelling combined. (d = .4, SD 6.69; $p < .001$). Improvement in narrative recall (d = .06; $p = .031$). Vocabulary improved more than narrative.	Combining narrative and vocabulary interventions made greater overall improvements. There was minimal improvement in expressive vocabulary use.
Pauls &	To assess	N=10	Pre-treatment: 2	Varied improvements in	Improvements were

Study	Objectives	Participants	Methods	Results	Conclusion
Archibald (2021)	impact of narrative-based intervention on working memory and academic skills.	Single subject interventions; No control.	sessions x 4 weeks. Treatment: 3 sessions x 5 weeks.	language. - Higher verbal short-term memory associated with better outcomes. - No clear consistent pattern of improvement in specific areas.	inconsistent across participants. (Some significant, others not). Possibility that verbal short-term memory skills improved outcomes for some.
Petersen et al. (2022)	To evaluate the impact of a multi-tiered system of language supports using the <i>Story Champs</i> program on narrative skills.	N=686 (349 control, 337 treatment) Range of students including those with DLD	Whole class with Tier 2 supports. 14 weeks; 2xweek (15-20 mins) with additional Tier 2 withdrawal for 10 weeks if needed.	Effect sizes ranged between 0.19 – 0.49 (p = 0.004 – 0.5). Narrative re-tells (d = 0.49) favoured treatment group. Tier 2: Narrative retells, personal generation, and expository retell (effect size 0.35 – 2.37). DLD Tier 2: effect size = 0.5.	Narrative intervention using Story Champs showed moderate to large effect sizes. - Tier 2 supports were effective, especially for students with DLD.
Plante et al. (2019)	To assess the effectiveness of enhanced conversational recasting with different densities of recasts on language learning.	N=20 10 received explicit teaching, 10 received implicit teaching.	Individual Therapy. 25 sessions, 30 mins x 5 days per week. Conditions: High-Density and Low-Density re-casts.	Analysis looked at age, mother's education, SPELT, P2, PPVT-4 and Shirts and Shoes test. No significance to results noted.	Dense recasting condition showed improved treatment efficacy. Low density showed significant improvement in articulation.
Storkel et al. (2019)	To compare the effects of dose and dose frequency on vocabulary learning in kindergarten children using an interactive book reading with explicit teaching of new words.	N=34, randomized into 4 groups. Not blinded.	Groups: A) Dose 6 mins. x Frequency 6, B) Dose 4 mins. x Dose Frequency 9 C) Dose 9 mins. x Dose Frequency 4 D) Control	All groups learned new vocabulary but there was significant forgetting of newly learned words occurred in all formats once treatment was withdrawn. 5-6 days later, only 40% of words remembered. 21 days later, only 30% recall.	Explicit teaching is helpful to those with DLD. Further research is required to determine the dosage and frequency for sustainability effect. Effective approach but must address retention.
Sutton et al. (2022)	To examine the influence of expressive and receptive	N=19 (Users of AAC for +2 years). 3 groups.	Individual treatment. 1 session with 4 tasks and unlimited time.	Results examined complexity of expressive communication. From ease of communication to most	Receptive and permanent events had better outcomes than expressive non-

Study	Objectives	Participants	Methods	Results	Conclusion
	language using AAC. Examiner acted out stories or events.			difficult were: comprehension, followed by interpretation (permanent), construction, interpretation (non-permanent).	permanent events/stories. Expression for individuals with DLD that are non-verbal requires greater research.
Wada et al. (2020)	To improve relative clauses in expressive language using structural priming combined with focused recasting.	N=26 (13 DLD, 13 TD) Convenience sample/ not blinded	Between subject design. Trials: 40 subject-focused, 40 object-focused relative clause trials. Duration: 1 session, no follow-up.	DLD learners needed slightly less than double the repetitions to master. DLD (M=26.04 times, SD 13.56) TD (14.73 times, SD 12.27). Significant main effects for prime type: TD: $F(1, 24) = 31.037$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 p = .564$ DLD: $F(1, 24) = 6.135$, $p < .05$, $\eta^2 p = .204$ Difference in rate of learning. TD faster. 3 of 11 DLD did not master learning threshold, 11 of 14 did not master object-focused learning. All TD did.	Both groups showed improvement in learning relative clauses. DLD children required more repetitions and struggled more with object-focused clauses. TD children were 1.9 times more likely to reach learning criterion. Significant effects for group and sentence type, with large partial eta squared values.
Wilcox et al. (2019)	To examine TELL (Teaching Early Literacy and Language) curriculum to promote oral language development and early literacy skills in early DLD learners.	N=318 children (with DLD or DSLI) 98 teachers involved Attrition: 29 children (17 TELL, 12 BAU) and 7 teachers	Design: RCT. Control: BAU. Duration: Full school year, daily. Teachers received PD and weekly/bi-weekly coaching. Measures: CELF, TOPEL, PALS PreK, receptive and expressive one-word picture test.	TELL effect size: Cohen's d 's .43 – 1.25. Vocabulary measures: Between-group effect sizes (Cohen's f^2 range from .02 to .44). No significant TELL effects for more distal measures. Expressive vocabulary test p values $< .0001$; $r = .5-.61$ (moderate to strong relationship).	Curriculum showed to have significant improvements on oral language and early literacy. There was a strong relationship between TELL and expressive vocabulary improvement. There were no significant effects on distal measures. PD and coaching were crucial to program.

5.2. Types of Treatments Intervention for Expressive Language Difficulties in DLD Children

The types of interventions originally sought for this review include: Visual Support Strategies (including Augmentative and Alternative Communication), Narrative Interventions, Peer-Mediated Interventions, Linguistic-Specific Interventions (including pragmatics, phonological awareness), Metacognitive Strategies and combined interventions. Finding quality research since 2017 was difficult and many promising studies in the end did not reach the threshold for research design to be included in this review. As previously stated, parent/caregiver led interventions were excluded due to issues of reliability and validity testing, alongside complex confounding variables inherent in the individual nature of the parent/caregivers as the delivery agent. Finding samples for each of these distinct categories proved to be a challenge, lowering the threshold for inclusion.

Visual Support Strategies is a category of expressive language intervention for children with DLD. It includes a wide range of visual aids, images, and forms of augmentative alternative communication (AAC) systems. These systems can be tailored to the specific needs of the student to assist in their expressive communication (Calder et al. 2020). It can reduce frustration of the individual with DLD because they can convey more of their thoughts and needs in a manner that typically developed individuals can understand (Cordier, et al., 2023). Visually supported communication can allow for increased participation in conversations and social interactions (Ebbels et al., 2024). Visually supported communication also builds vocabulary through consistent representations of items. It makes abstract concepts more concrete (Lavelli et al., 2019). Although this review focuses on expressive language, it should also be noted that using visual supports can increase understanding by pairing language with visuals. It can increase independence and help individuals with lower verbal output advocate for themselves. By pairing verbal output with visual supports, children with DLD can be more clearly understood and more fully participate in social and academic communication.

Narrative Interventions are a promising approach for children with DLD and expressive language challenges. Through narrative interventions, the most complex form of communication can be addressed. It can promote storytelling, summarizing, vocabulary expansion and sequential ordering. With practice, and enhanced milieu techniques, children with DLD can improve their conversational communication, thereby strengthening their social interactions and pragmatics by extension. Being fluid in the structure of telling a story, narrative speaking skills reinforce story schemas for greater transferability. At its best, narrative interventions support a naturalized acquisition of expressive language skills that are tailored to the individual's interests and evolving linguistic skills. This style of intervention hopes to promote memory and retention. Understanding the schema of narration, children with DLD can also improve their comprehension skills. As narrative skills represent the most complex system of communication, once achieved, the child with DLD can improve their expressive language broadly.

The third type of study intervention explored were peer-mediated interventions. In these more naturalized settings, a great deal of variability exists. Peer-mediated interventions are of significance to the child with DLD. They promote social interactions and communication skills through inclusivity. Unfortunately, these studies are challenging to replicate as the confounding variables are difficult to eliminate. They have less of a benefit for the typically developing student and a clear impact on children with DLD.

The fourth intervention study design was metacognitive in approach. Many studies that use explicit teaching methods exploring metacognition training show promise in other educational fields (von Thienen et al., 2023). Teaching individuals with DLD how their brain is processing the information and what the "thinking" is behind the pattern being trained shows to reinforce or deepen the neural connection to the learning. This in turn, strengthens the comprehension and increases the possibility of transferability to words, sentence structures, phonological patterns or morphemes that follow the same rules. Intuitively, the author felt that this promise would be transferrable into the DLD field. Although studies included did show some

potential, the effect size of these studies were more variable along with the longevity of the outcomes. The aspiration of transferability was also not as profound as hoped for.

The final category of intervention considered was the multifaceted/ combined approach. The assumption is based upon the uniqueness of individuals and their needs. The hope with combined approaches is that the applicability of such practices can service a wider audience and be delivered with confidence of effect across populations. The universal design and delivery as a tier one whole-class approach has great appeal throughout the education system. If effective, this approach could then reduce the financial need for specialized interventions in smaller groups. The challenges with this approach also highlight the confounding variables of teacher/professional efficacy, commitment and understanding of the larger process. The needs of a multitude of children simultaneously are a much more complicated teaching process than a singular approach for small set of learners. The wider the diversity of the learners, both with DLD needs and without, lessens the ability to focus on a rate of pace and repetition that met the majority of the learners needs. This approach, although proposed for broader applications brought into question its replicability and reliability of results. These considerations for this type of intervention will be examined within the Findings section.

With the research question seeking to determine the most beneficial intervention approach for DLD learners, five methods were considered. They included Visual Support Strategies (including Augmentative and Alternative Communication), Narrative Interventions, Peer-Mediated Interventions, Linguistic-Specific Interventions (including pragmatics, phonological awareness, Metacognitive Strategies and combined interventions. With each of these methods identified areas of concern must be noted, while contrasting with the potential effect size of the outcomes.

5.3. Implementation Methods

Another important consideration for intervention methods includes the format of the program. In this section, we will note the most common approaches within DLD interventions. The twenty studies included in this analytical review used a combination of these intervention approaches.

From a universal design, interventions that can be applied to a *whole-class*, most appropriate in a school setting, is the most cost-effective approach. This requires highly trained, intuitive, and consistent professionals that can adapt to the needs of a few whilst providing what the majority needs to advance their language skills. Integrating language interventions into the classroom environment is ultimate goal of approaches. Other models include consultation and support between educators and specialized staff such as SLPs or *language intervention specialist*. These higher intensity options for intervention are more precise but more costly (both to the individual and to the system). They often reflect a withdrawal approach that can lead to social challenges and competing demands for contact with peers and other learning experiences. The use of small group and direct individual therapies have benefits to the individual with greater responsiveness by the interventionist. *Narrative-based Language Interventions* focus on practising the compromised skill that children with DLD and expressive barriers need, but they can be artificial in approach. The Child with DLD can struggle to transfer these skills even in slightly different contexts. *Peer-mediated interventions* often address both the naturalized environment application and strengthening the social connection between typically developing and children with DLD. They require a commitment of the peer that sometimes is difficult to maintain. *Pragmatic language skills training* focuses on the structures within social language. They include turn-taking, following agreed upon rules of a game, topic continuance and understanding when it is appropriate to speak or use formal or less formal language. *Phonological Awareness* training involves the explicit teaching of manipulating sound production. It connects sounds with diction and letters to improve expressive language accuracy and confidence. *Computer-Assisted Language Intervention* is a growing field of intervention and support. Although standalone C-ALI programs have tenuous applicability, C-ALI is a growing field with AI capacity that supports express language development in the whole-classroom setting

(Efthymiou, 2024). Each of the intervention approaches showed promise for the DLD in specific controlled environments, but this review was to look for the greatest efficacy for expressive language.

The intervention design and intervention approach are strongly linked in predicting the effectiveness of a DLD intervention for improving expressive language in children with DLD. The understanding the specific profiles of the children with DLD and expressive language weakness is critical in determining the most appropriate intervention approach. Availability should not be the sole consideration whether a child will be best served by a specific intervention.

6. Findings

Various interventions were noted to have mixed results for improving expressive language in children with developmental language disorders. Although many of the conditions for each study were different, based on study design and results, there were four forms of interventions that show the greatest opportunity for expansion. These were only partially what the author had anticipated.

Firstly, Visual Supports and Structured Interventions (VS), as seen in SHAPE CODING and various visual supports offers the greatest promise for improving expressive language in children with DLD. Because children with DLD do not visual language in the same manner as typically developing children do, the visual coding support reminds and prepares a visual structure for communication (Calder et al., 2020). Calder and colleagues' study (2020) showed notable improvement, but with no control and possible biases, results should be tempered. Balthazar and colleagues' (2018) study was absent a control and although some improvement was noted, the lack of significance between dosages within the trials speaks to a need for further establish thresholds of diminishing returns. The more recent study from 2020 became somewhat confusing or perhaps more difficult to analyse based upon the comparison between Meta Taal, SHAPE CODING and CSI. Without clear controls, the possibility of confounding factors could be at play.

The second most promising approach was one that used explicit teaching methods through Linguistic-Specific Interventions (LSI). Paralleling current effective reading interventions, explicit teaching is important for children that do not intuitively learn the structures of language. The importance of systematic and structured approaches to teaching language assist in the development of language structure. Balthazar and Scott (2018) and Gillam et al. (2017) shared findings that direct teaching led to better grammar understanding, general sentence structures and story organization patterns. Plante et al. (2019) was exploring dosage and frequency in their linguistic- specific intervention. In this case, it lacked significant differences between high-density and low-density conditions of recasting frequency. Eidsvag and colleagues (2018) also lacked statistical differences in group outcomes. This highlighted that paired learning was not creating greater density of learning- suggesting that language learning is so challenging for children with DLD that they do not attend to someone else's learning as a typically developing child might. The short intervention could explain the lower sustainability of the learning. Similarly, Finestack and colleagues' (2018) short duration may affect the generalizability of the findings. With these skills developed, improved expression occurred amongst participants in their studies. Through explicit teaching and a great deal of repetition children with DLD can improve their expressive language. This category of intervention was the most common of the studies in this analytical review.

The third intervention category of consideration were the narrative intervention (NI) formats, as they focused on the skill of expressive language holistically. The hope in these studies were to increase transferability into naturalized settings. Studies such as Joffe and colleagues (2017) included moderate effect sizes, but relied on teacher reports, thus introducing possible bias. Goldfield and colleagues (2022) had the benefit of larger sample sizes but showed great variability in results between the smaller study to this larger scale. This highlighted the issues of scalability. Pauls and Archibald (2021) was compromised by the absence of a control group. With mixed results, it comes into question the effectiveness of the intervention. Petersen et al. (2022) echoed the lack of control group and the variable outcomes as Pauls and Archibald (2021) study.

So too, must one consider the intervention's impact across setting, despite some moderate to large effect sizes. Narrative Interventions holds promise and clear future research is indicated.

The fourth type of intervention, peer-mediated (PM) addresses two key aspects of the child with DLD's typical profile. For many children with DLD they have weakened social connections. Peer-mediation offers relationship building in a protected space, but also brings into consideration the confounding factors of individual peers' commitment and interest in the process. Chen and colleagues (2020) attempted a broader approach, not specific to just DLD. In this study biases related to teacher and caregiver reports are a concern. The study had a variety of children with disabilities included so what may be most effective for a child with DLD and other disabilities may differ. Blaskova (2021) peer-mediated case study had a very small sample size (N=14), relied on qualitative measures reducing the reliability of the results. Although peer-mediated approaches increase social connection, real-world practice and milieu enhanced settings, the variability and small scale of most studies also indicate future research opportunities.

Strengths and Limitations of Studies

Overall, the four categories of intervention approaches highlight areas of needs for children with DLD and expressive language challenges. Peer-mediation addresses social connection, linguistic-specific attempts to target the foundational pieces of expressive language, narrative intervention provides practice in expressive language and visual supports help support the weaken language processing in the brain. All have value as a DLD intervention approach.

The following table ranks the twenty studies included in this review. Using effect size as a key ranking component, size of the sample, and design quality some of the studies showed the greater promise. Interventions by category did not rank in clusters. This leads to questions of reliability, validity and implementation for further research. It also highlights the individuality of the children with DLD's learning profiles. There were four studies for various reasons that could have been eliminated due to design weakness or sample size, but the author included them to provide comparison across intervention types. Those studies are noted at the bottom of the table.

Table 3.

Ranked comparison of studies under consideration. LSI – Linguistic-Specific Intervention, Visual Support, Narrative Intervention, Peer Mediation.

Rank	Author and Year	Quality of Study Design	Intervention Type	Justification of Ranking
1	Calder et al., 2020	RCT, strong design	Visual supports (SHAPE CODING) (VS)	Large effect sizes; treatment group showed significant improvement maintained post-intervention.
2	Balthazar & Scott, 2018	High quality, robust design	Explicit teaching (LSI)	Significant gains in language; large effect sizes for targeted grammatical structures.
3	Ebbels et al., 2024	Individual, robust analysis	Morphosyntactic intervention (LSI)	Highly significant improvement (Cohen d = 1.6); effective methods for enhancing memory.
4	Finestack et al., 2018	RCT, randomized groups	Teaching grammar (LSI)	Significant differences found based on teaching methods; effective framework established.
5	Joffe et al., 2017	RCT, specific focus	Narrative & vocabulary (NI, LSI)	Various improvements in narrative and vocabulary tasks; overall significant gains.
6	Gillam et al.,	Single-subject,	Narrative discourse intervention	Moderate to large gains in narrative

Rank	Author and Year	Quality of Study Design	Intervention Type	Justification of Ranking
	2017	detailed	(NI)	productivity and complexity; strong individual results.
7	Wilcox et al., 2019	RCT, strong study design	TELL (Teaching Early Literacy and Language) (LSI, VS, NI)	Significant improvements in vocabulary measures; positive impact on oral language development.
8	Sutton et al., 2022	Individual sessions, reasonable	AAC (Augmentative and Alternative Communication) (VS)	Strong correlations and improvements in expressive communication tasks over time.
9	Wada et al., 2020	Between-subject design	Structural priming combined with recasting (NI, LSI)	Both groups improved; highlights challenges for DLD children requiring more repetitions.
10	Calder et al., 2018	Moderate quality	Past tense intervention (LSI)	Significant progress in using past tense; moderate sample size and effect evidence.
11	Balthazar et al., 2020	Mixed methods	Complex Sentence Intervention (LSI, VS)	Various effect sizes reported for different approaches; highlights the need for further research.
12	Aguilar et al., 2018	Modest quality, small sample	Sublexical training (LSI)	High variability showed better retention; modest effect size and significant interactions.
13	Eidsvag et al., 2018	RCT, well-structured	Conversational recasting (NI)	No significant differences; moderate effect sizes; needs more specific targeted approach.
14	Petersen et al., 2022	Strong RCT, multi-tiered	Narrative intervention (NI)	Significant improvements in narrative retelling; good design with moderate effect sizes.
15	Plante et al., 2019	Controlled design	Enhanced conversational recasting (NI)	Evidence of effective interventions; outcomes showed no significant differences.
16	Storkel et al., 2019	Randomized groups	Interactive book reading (NI)	All groups learned, but significant forgetting noted after intervention ended.
17	Blaskova, 2021	High risk design, case study	Peer relationship impact (PM)	Limited generalizability; did not report effect sizes; qualitative findings.
18	Goldfield et al., 2022	High risk design, mixed methods	Narrative intervention (NI)	Mixed results; did not replicate earlier findings effectively; lower effects seen.
19	Pauls & Archibald, 2021	High risk design, single-subject	Narrative intervention (NI)	Varied outcomes, no consistent patterns; limited data on effectiveness.
20	Chen et al., 2020	High risk design, confounding variables	Whole class intervention (LSI, VS, NI)	Significant z-score differences but confounded reporting; lack of robustness in findings.

Within the twenty studies reviewed for this article many truths are apparent. DLD is a pernicious condition that has far reaching implications across the lifespan. There is still debate in the research about the most effective intervention approach, the dosage, frequency, generalization and long-term impact of various programs. Equally as compelling are the significant improvements in targeted language skills through explicit, intentional training for children with DLD. Calder and colleagues (2020) reported large effect sizes ($d = 3.03$) for past tense use and these improvements were maintained over follow-up periods. Explicit teaching and modelling techniques also showed significant growth with complex sentence production; particularly adverbial (SMD $p = .91$) and relative clauses (SMD $p = 1.00$) (Balthazar & Scott, 2018). Balthazar and colleagues (2020) furthered that evidence with complex sentence intervention including subordinate clauses. Additionally, although some studies showed weaker study design, others had rigorous designs with randomized controlled trials, single-subject experimental designs and multiple-baseline methodologies. Chen et al. (2020) examined peer language effects in inclusive classrooms. The promise of universal design for mainstream applications acts to highlight possible brighter, more inclusive experience for children with DLD.

7. Implications of the Studies

DLD acts as a barrier for many children and adults alike. The future faced by children with DLD, without mitigation is bleak for many. By applying some of the language specific interventions, coupling with visual supports and addressing the narrative production pragmatically, one would assume highly strengthened language production. What is clear is that children with DLD need specific supports tailored to their profile of needs. The children do not extract language learning through implicit exposure, but through explicit training with significant repetition. How much repetition, how frequent the exposure and how long do intervention programs need to be is less clear.

Unexpectedly, a larger scale, universal administration, multi-modal approach did not garner the expected results. Despite highly supported with master-mentors, the variation between classrooms and confounding variables led to less-than-hoped for outcomes. The complexity of DLD makes it difficult to universally attempt to address all needs. The need for precision and a high degree of repetition before moving on is highlighted in the studies explored.

8. Implications from the Research

This analytical review sought to compare visual support systems, linguistic-specific interventions, peer-mediated and narrative interventions to determine a more efficacious intervention type for children with DLD and expressive language challenges. What was found, is that specific approaches varied in their effect sizes and confounding variables weakened results and generalizability broadly. Report bias and selection bias brought into question reliability and validity of some results. Settings and specialized training did not predict the effect size of the study. If individuals are properly trained, most professionals are capable of administering intervention programs with efficacy.

9. Future Research Opportunities

DLD is a less researched field of study relative to its prevalence. The twenty studies reviewed showed variability in results, indicating that there a number of potential areas of further investigation. First and foremost, DLD profiles feature a need to deep repetition to ensure learning. Although studies varied in the dosage, frequency, intensity of the intervention's clear lines of delineation for points of diminishing return were inconsistent. Determining optimal dosage and frequency must be a focus moving forward as to assure long-term growth that is sustainable. Long-term cohort studies that track and follow participants over the lifespan or at least into adulthood could offer a number of important insights. Studies that would explore the

transferability of learning into both functional and academic settings would be a significant leap forward child with DLD. Somewhat limited generalization was noted in the studies compared. By establishing program parameters that could lead to naturalized transference, those with DLD would experience less barriers across settings. Peer and social interaction studies would be of interest for future research. Strengthening connection to language-rich individuals and settings may give the repetition that children DLD need in order to internalize their learning. Peer interactions, clearly assist as a protective factor for future well-being, employment and overall happiness. Finally, studies that probe more diverse population and diagnoses could assist in more inclusive environments for many equity seeking communities.

10. Conclusion

Developmental Language Disorder (DLD) is a pervasive disability that impacts a person across their lifespan. Individuals with DLD and specifically expressive language challenges often struggle with educational outcomes (Adlof & Hogan, 2019; Rinaldi et al., 2021), inter-personal connections, social isolation (Ash et al., 2020; Hendricks et al., 2019, Kilpatrick et al. 2019), mental health (particularly depression) (Kilpatrick et al. 2019; Rinaldi et al., 2021) and low self-esteem (Conti-Ramsden & Durkin, 2012). Despite these realities many children are not diagnosed early, with hesitancy of professionals to label children early. But it is early intervention that makes the most profound impact on children with DLD's trajectory.

This analytical review examined 20 studies published in 2017 or more recently that addressed express language of children with DLD. The studies fell into the categories of Visual Supports, Linguistic-Specific Interventions, Narrative Interventions, Peer-Mediated and a combination of the four types. The studies ranged from small case studies to larger comparative projects. Each study was looked at for quality using the Cochrane Bias Tool. Effect Size (predominately p or Cohen d) and outcome measures were compared. Delivery agents included Speech and Language Pathologists, Specially-trained Teachers and Research Assistants. Excluded from the analytical review were parent and caregiver delivery agents as reliability was deemed lower in those studies.

The research questions explored were: Was there a preeminent intervention form that showed the greatest effect size? How did report bias and selection bias influence the reliability and validity of the findings? And, did multi-modality models improve outcomes? The research suggests that no one intervention approach garnered superior outcomes consistently. Reliability and validity weakness in some studies prevent generalization and offer future research opportunities. Trained delivery agents are an important aspect to the reliability of the implementation and expected outcomes. Less reliable results were seen where teacher reporting skewed the evidence. And perhaps most disappointing, whole-class universal designed implementation on a larger scale did not provide the results that were hoped for. Multi-modality, did not in fact, lead to better outcome results.

There is much to be hopeful within the studies selected. Intervention does make a difference for children with DLD. Explicit, repeated teaching coupled with enhanced milieu settings saw improvement in narrative expression. Even when studies did not conclusive show large effect sizes, they did indicate progress for the children within the study and set clear future research opportunities.

Children with DLD represents upwards to 31% of the population (Donolato et al., 2023). These children often get missed in their identification and therefore lag in receiving the supports they need to excel. In recent years, the awareness of Developmental Language Disorders has increased, opening the door for more robust research. We are seeing the initial pieces of exploration and advancement that will lead to evidence-based research to support children with DLD and expressive language barriers. It is too important not to continue to seek opportunities to support these young learners.

11. References

Adlof, S. M., & Hogan, T. P. (2019). If We Don't Look, We Won't See: Measuring Language Development to Inform Literacy Instruction. *Policy Insights from the Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 6(2), 210–217. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2372732219839075>

Aguilar, J. M., Plante, E., & Sandoval, M. (2018). Exemplar Variability Facilitates Retention of Word Learning by Children with Specific Language Impairment. *Language, speech, and hearing services in schools*, 49(1), 72–84. https://doi.org/10.1044/2017_LSHSS-17-0031

Ash, A. C., Christopoulos, T. T., & Redmond, S. M. (2020). “Tell Me About Your Child”: A Grounded Theory Study of Mothers’ Understanding of Language Disorder. *American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology*, 29(2), 819–840. https://doi.org/10.1044/2020_AJSLP-19-00064

Balthazar, C. H., Ebbels, S., & Zwitserlood, R. (2020). Explicit Grammatical Intervention for Developmental Language Disorder: Three Approaches. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools*, 51(2), 226–246. https://doi.org/10.1044/2019_LSHSS-19-00046

Balthazar, C. H., & Scott, C. M. (2018). Targeting Complex Sentences in Older School Children With Specific Language Impairment: Results From an Early-Phase Treatment Study. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 61(3), 713–728. https://doi.org/10.1044/2017_JSLHR-L-17-0105

Benschop, N., Nuijten, A. L. P., Keil, M., Rohde, K. I. M., Lee, J. S., & Commandeur, H. R. (2021). Construal level theory and escalation of commitment. *Theory and Decision*, 91(1), 135–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11238-020-09794-w>

Bishop, D. V. M., Snowling, M. J., Thompson, P. A., Greenhalgh, T., & and the CATALISE-2 consortium. (2017). Phase 2 of CATALISE: a multinational and multidisciplinary Delphi consensus study of problems with language development: Terminology. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 58(10), 1068–1080. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.12721>

Blaskova, L. (2021). *Peer relationships and the wellbeing of children with Developmental Language Disorder* [Apollo - University of Cambridge Repository]. <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.81115>

Brownlie, E. B., Jabbar, A., Beitchman, J., Vida, R., & Atkinson, L. (2007). Language Impairment and Sexual Assault of Girls and Women: Findings from a Community Sample. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, 35(4), 618–626. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10802-007-9117-4>

Bruinsma, G., Wijnen, F., & Gerrits, E. (2023). Language gains in 4–6-year-old children with developmental language disorder and the relation with language profile, severity, multilingualism and non-verbal cognition. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 58(3), 765–785. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1460-6984.12821>

Calder, S. D., Claessen, M., Ebbels, S., & Leitão, S. (2020). Explicit Grammar Intervention in Young School-Aged Children With Developmental Language Disorder: An Efficacy Study Using Single-Case Experimental Design. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools*, 51(2), 298–316. https://doi.org/10.1044/2019_LSHSS-19-00060

Calder, S. D., Claessen, M., Ebbels, S., & Leitão, S. (2021). The Efficacy of an Explicit Intervention Approach to Improve Past Tense Marking for Early School-Age Children With Developmental Language Disorder. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research, 64*(1), 91–104. https://doi.org/10.1044/2020_JSLHR-20-00132

Cappadona, I., Ielo, A., La Fauci, M., Tresoldi, M., Settimo, C., De Cola, M. C., Muratore, R., De Domenico, C., Di Cara, M., Corallo, F., Tripodi, E., Impallomeni, C., Quartarone, A., & Cucinotta, F. (2023). Feasibility and Effectiveness of Speech Intervention Implemented with a Virtual Reality System in Children with Developmental Language Disorders: A Pilot Randomized Control Trial. *Children, 10*(8), 1336. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10081336>

Carson, L., Baker, E., & Munro, N. (2022). A systematic review of interventions for late talkers: intervention approaches, elements, and vocabulary outcomes. *American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology, 31*(6), 2861-2874.

Chen, J., Justice, L. M., Tambyraja, S. R., & Sawyer, B. (2020). Exploring the mechanism through which peer effects operate in preschool classrooms to influence language growth. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly, 53*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2020.02.002>

Conti-Ramsden, G., Botting, N., & Durkin, K. (2008). Parental perspectives during the transition to adulthood of adolescents with a history of specific language impairment (SLI). *Journal of speech, language, and hearing research : JSLHR, 51*(1), 84–96. [https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388\(2008/006\)](https://doi.org/10.1044/1092-4388(2008/006))

Conti-Ramsden, G., & Durkin, K. (2012). Postschool Educational and Employment Experiences of Young People With Specific Language Impairment. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools, 43*(4), 507–520. [https://doi.org/10.1044/0161-1461\(2012/11-0067\)](https://doi.org/10.1044/0161-1461(2012/11-0067))

Conti-Ramsden, G., Durkin, K., Toseeb, U., Botting, N., & Pickles, A. (2018). Education and employment outcomes of young adults with a history of developmental language disorder. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders, 53*(2), 237–255. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1460-6984.12338>

Cullen, H., Billingham, S., & St Clair, M. C. (2024). How do children with language disorder perceive their peer interactions? A qualitative investigation. *Autism & Developmental Language Impairments, 9*, 23969415241275775.

Donolato, E., Toffalini, E., Rogde, K., Nordahl-Hansen, A., Lervåg, A., Norbury, C., & Melby-Lervåg, M. (2023). Oral language interventions can improve language outcomes in children with neurodevelopmental disorders: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Campbell Systematic Reviews, 19*(4), e1368. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cl2.1368>

Eadie, P., Conway, L., Hallenstein, B., Mensah, F., McKean, C., & Reilly, S. (2018). Quality of life in children with developmental language disorder. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders, 53*(4), 799–810. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1460-6984.12385>

Ebbels, S. H., Gadd, M., Nicoll, H., Hughes, L., Dawson, N., Burke, C., Calder, S. D., & Frizelle, P. (2024). The Effectiveness of Individualized Morphosyntactic Target Identification and Explicit Intervention Using the SHAPE CODING System for Children With Developmental Language Disorder and the Impact of Within-

Session Dosage. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools*, 55(3), 803–837.
https://doi.org/10.1044/2024_LSHSS-23-00098

Ebbels, S. H., McCartney, E., Slonims, V., Dockrell, J. E., & Norbury, C. F. (2019). Evidence-based pathways to intervention for children with language disorders. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders*, 54(1), 3–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1460-6984.12387>

Efthymiou, E. (2024). Empowering Language: Fostering Inclusion and Growth Through Assistive Intelligence for Students With Language Disorders. In *Childhood Developmental Language Disorders: Role of Inclusion, Families, and Professionals* (pp. 17-31). IGI Global.

Eidsvåg, S. S., Plante, E., Oglivie, T., Privette, C., & Mailend, M. L. (2019). Individual Versus Small Group Treatment of Morphological Errors for Children With Developmental Language Disorder. *Language, speech, and hearing services in schools*, 50(2), 237–252. https://doi.org/10.1044/2018_LSHSS-18-0033

Favot, K., Carter, M., & Stephenson, J. (2021). The Effects of Oral Narrative Intervention on the Narratives of Children with Language Disorder: a Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Developmental and Physical Disabilities*, 33(4), 489–536. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10882-020-09763-9>

Finestack, L. H. (2018). Evaluation of an Explicit Intervention to Teach Novel Grammatical Forms to Children With Developmental Language Disorder. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 61(8), 2062–2075. https://doi.org/10.1044/2018_JSLHR-L-17-0339

Forrest, C. L., Gibson, J. L., & St Clair, M. C. (2021). Social Functioning as a Mediator between Developmental Language Disorder (DLD) and Emotional Problems in Adolescents. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(3), 1221. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18031221>

Gillam, S. L., Olszewski, A., Squires, K., Wolfe, K., Slocum, T., & Gillam, R. B. (2018). Improving Narrative Production in Children With Language Disorders: An Early-Stage Efficacy Study of a Narrative Intervention Program. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools*, 49(2), 197–212. https://doi.org/10.1044/2017_LSHSS-17-0047

Glasby, J., Graham, L. J., White, S. L. J., & Tancredi, H. (2022). Do teachers know enough about the characteristics and educational impacts of Developmental Language Disorder (DLD) to successfully include students with DLD? *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 119, 103868. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2022.103868>

Goldfeld, S., Snow, P., Eadie, P., Munro, J., Gold, L., Le, H. N. D., Orsini, F., Shingles, B., Connell, J., Watts, A., & Barnett, T. (2022). Classroom Promotion of Oral Language: Outcomes From a Randomized Controlled Trial of a Whole-of-Classroom Intervention to Improve Children's Reading Achievement. *AERA Open*, 8, 233285842211315. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23328584221131530>

Hendricks, A. E., Adlof, S. M., Alonzo, C. N., Fox, A. B., & Hogan, T. P. (2019). Identifying Children at Risk for Developmental Language Disorder Using a Brief, Whole-Classroom Screen. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 62(4), 896–908. https://doi.org/10.1044/2018_JSLHR-L-18-0093

- Hutchins, C., & Schmitt, M. B. (2024). Group Size: An Active Ingredient of School-Based Language Therapy. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools, 55*(3), 781–802. https://doi.org/10.1044/2024_LSHSS-23-00047
- Jensen De López, K. M., Kraljević, J. K., & Struntze, E. L. B. (2022). Efficacy, model of delivery, intensity and targets of pragmatic interventions for children with developmental language disorder: A systematic review. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders, 57*(4), 764–781. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1460-6984.12716>
- Joffe, V. L., Rixon, L., & Hulme, C. (2019). Improving storytelling and vocabulary in secondary school students with language disorder: a randomized controlled trial. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders, 54*(4), 656–672. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1460-6984.12471>
- Kilpatrick, T., Leitão, S., & Boyes, M. (2019). Mental health in adolescents with a history of developmental language disorder: The moderating effect of bullying victimisation. *Autism & Developmental Language Impairments, 4*, 239694151989331. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2396941519893313>
- Lavelli, M., Barachetti, C., Majorano, M., Florit, E., Brotto, C., & Miottello, P. (2019). Impacts of a shared book-reading intervention for Italian-speaking children with developmental language disorder. *International Journal of Language & Communication Disorders, 54*(4), 565–579. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1460-6984.12460>
- Law, J., Garrett, Z., & Nye, C. (2003). Speech and language therapy interventions for children with primary speech and language delay or disorder. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, 2015*(5). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD004110>
- Law, J., Rush, R., Schoon, I., & Parsons, S. (2009). Modeling developmental language difficulties from school entry into adulthood: Literacy, mental health, and employment outcomes.
- Law, M., Stewart, D., Letts, L., Pollock, N., Bosch, J., & Westmorland, M. (1998). Guidelines for critical review of qualitative studies. *McMaster University occupational therapy evidence-based practice research Group, 1*.
- McGregor, K. K. (2020). How We Fail Children With Developmental Language Disorder. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools, 51*(4), 981–992. https://doi.org/10.1044/2020_LSHSS-20-00003
- McGregor, K. K., Van Horne, A. O., Curran, M., Cook, S. W., & Cole, R. (2021). The Challenge of Rich Vocabulary Instruction for Children With Developmental Language Disorder. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools, 52*(2), 467–484. https://doi.org/10.1044/2020_LSHSS-20-00110
- McKean, C., Reilly, S., Bavin, E. L., Bretherton, L., Cini, E., Conway, L., Cook, F., Eadie, P., Prior, M., Wake, M., & Mensah, F. (2017). Language Outcomes at 7 Years: Early Predictors and Co-Occurring Difficulties. *Pediatrics, 139*(3), e20161684. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-1684>
- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., & PRISMA Group (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *PLoS medicine, 6*(7), e1000097. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000097>

Moll, K. (2022). Comorbidity of Reading Disorders. In M. J. Snowling, C. Hulme, & K. Nation (Eds.), *The Science of Reading* (1st ed., pp. 439–459). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119705116.ch20>

Norbury, C. F., Gooch, D., Wray, C., Baird, G., Charman, T., Simonoff, E., Vamvakas, G., & Pickles, A. (2016). The impact of nonverbal ability on prevalence and clinical presentation of language disorder: evidence from a population study. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, *57*(11), 1247–1257. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.12573>

Pauls, L. J., & Archibald, L. M. (2021). Cognitive and linguistic effects of narrative-based language intervention in children with Developmental Language Disorder. *Autism & Developmental Language Impairments*, *6*, 239694152110158. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23969415211015867>

Petersen, D. B., Staskowski, M., Spencer, T. D., Foster, M. E., & Brough, M. P. (2022). The Effects of a Multitiered System of Language Support on Kindergarten Oral and Written Language: A Large-Scale Randomized Controlled Trial. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools*, *53*(1), 44–68. https://doi.org/10.1044/2021_LSHSS-20-00162

Plante, E., Mettler, H. M., Tucci, A., & Vance, R. (2019). Maximizing Treatment Efficiency in Developmental Language Disorder: Positive Effects in Half the Time. *American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology*, *28*(3), 1233–1247. https://doi.org/10.1044/2019_AJSLP-18-0285

Pomper, R., McGregor, K. K., Arbisi-Kelm, T., Eden, N., & Ohlmann, N. (2022). Direct Instruction Improves Word Learning for Children With Developmental Language Disorder. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, *65*(11), 4228–4249. https://doi.org/10.1044/2022_JSLHR-22-00300

Rinaldi, S., Caselli, M. C., Cofelice, V., D’Amico, S., De Cagno, A. G., Della Corte, G., Di Martino, M. V., Di Costanzo, B., Levorato, M. C., Penge, R., Rossetto, T., Sansavini, A., Vecchi, S., & Zoccolotti, P. (2021). Efficacy of the Treatment of Developmental Language Disorder: A Systematic Review. *Brain Sciences*, *11*(3), 407. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11030407>

Schmitt, M. B., Tambyraja, S., & Hutchins, C. (2022). Story Champs: changing the narrative on oral language intervention¹. *Evidence-Based Communication Assessment and Intervention*, *16*(2), 52–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17489539.2022.2089042>

Salmenlinna, I., & Laakso, M. (2020). Other-initiations of repair by children with developmental language disorder in speech-language therapy and non-institutional play. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, *34*(10-11), 894-909.

Schmitt, M. B., Tambyraja, S., & Siddiqui, S. (2022). Peer Effects in Language Therapy for Preschoolers With Developmental Language Disorder: A Pilot Study. *American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology*, *31*(4), 1854–1867. https://doi.org/10.1044/2022_AJSLP-21-00313

Segura-Pujol, H., & Briones-Rojas, C. (2021). Treatment intensity for developmental language disorder: A systematic review. *International Journal of Speech-Language Pathology*, *23*(5), 465–474. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17549507.2020.1856412>

Shadiev, R., & Yang, M. (2020). Review of Studies on Technology-Enhanced Language Learning and Teaching. *Sustainability*, *12*(2), 524. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12020524>

Storkel, H. L., Komesidou, R., Pezold, M. J., Pitt, A. R., Fleming, K. K., & Romine, R. S. (2019). The Impact of Dose and Dose Frequency on Word Learning by Kindergarten Children With Developmental Language Disorder During Interactive Book Reading. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools, 50*(4), 518–539. https://doi.org/10.1044/2019_LSHSS-VOIA-18-0131

Tarvainen, S., Launonen, K., & Stolt, S. (2021). Oral language comprehension interventions in school-age children and adolescents with developmental language disorder: A systematic scoping review. *Autism & Developmental Language Impairments, 6*, 239694152110104. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23969415211010423>

Telesca, L. (2024). Implementing a Metalinguistic Approach to Secondary School Writing. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools, 55*(1), 34–55. https://doi.org/10.1044/2023_LSHSS-22-00182

Tomblin, J. B., Zhang, X., Buckwalter, P., & Catts, H. (2000). The Association of Reading Disability, Behavioral Disorders, and Language Impairment among Second-grade Children. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry, 41*(4), 473–482. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1469-7610.00632>

von Thienen, J. P., Weinstein, T. J., & Meinel, C. (2023). Creative metacognition in design thinking: exploring theories, educational practices, and their implications for measurement. *Frontiers in Psychology, 14*, 1157001.

Wada, R., Gillam, S. L., & Gillam, R. B. (2020). The Use of Structural Priming and Focused Recasts to Facilitate the Production of Subject- and Object-Focused Relative Clauses by School-Age Children with and Without Developmental Language Disorder. *American Journal of Speech-Language Pathology, 29*(4), 1883–1895. https://doi.org/10.1044/2020_AJSLP-19-00090

Wilcox, M. J., Gray, S., & Reiser, M. (2020). Preschoolers with developmental speech and/or language impairment: Efficacy of the Teaching Early Literacy and Language (TELL) curriculum. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly, 51*, 124–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2019.10.005>

Yarian, M., Washington, K. N., Spencer, C. E., Vannest, J., & Crowe, K. (2021). Exploring Predictors of Expressive Grammar Across Different Assessment Tasks in Preschoolers With or Without DLD. *Communication Disorders Quarterly, 42*(2), 111–121. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525740119868238>